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Artificial Intelligence A Threat or a Boon to Humanity?

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Abstract: Machines are evolving and we humans are witnesses to this evolution. Our lives are changing rapidly during this age of Artificial Intelligence. From Google search to our money transactions Artificial intelligence plays an important role in our day to day life. Despite of learning and engaging with this new technology we can't help but worry - Is AI really coming for our jobs? If yes, which jobs and sectors will be affected by it and which won't? There are various controversies over the rise of Artificial Intelligence. This write-up will shed some light on various aspects of Artificial intelligence, it's advantages, disadvantages and help us decide if AI is really a threat or a boon to humanity. It's time we figure out our role as humans in this age of Machine evolution, or should we say, machine revolution?

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence (AI), Artificial General Intelligence (AGI), Technology development, Artificial Intelligence applications, Machine Learning.

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Introduction

It was today morning; I came across a news article on the internet saying “Amazon Opens A Supermarket With No Checkouts” (Golden 2020). Very intrigued I clicked on the link to read more. I found out that Amazon has opened a supermarket in Seattle with no checkout operators or self-service tills, all with the help of computer vision and machine learning. It uses hundreds of ceiling-mounted cameras and electronic sensors to identify each customer, tracks the items they select and adds them to customers’ Amazon Go account. There’s no need for any human interaction at all! This has left me wondering, how far are we in the age of AI? Moreover, what it’s like being human in the age of AI?

While some of us are still trying to figure out the difference between artificial intelligence and machine learning, AI is fast progressing.

This breakthrough technology has already become accessible for any software developer; tech giants are currently competing to dominate the field of artificial intelligence. China has taken serious steps to

This essay will take us through various aspects and applications of AI and how most people misinterpret it as something to be scared about. It explains how we can benefit from AI and use it for the development and betterment of humanity.

become the leader in AI. Technology has come a long way. Previously humans had a lot of vanity as to being the most intelligent species on earth, thanks to Dietrich Prinz and Christopher Strachey who collaborated and proved us wrong in 1951 by writing the first working AI program to run on the Ferranti Mark 1 machine: a checkers-playing

program. Since then machines have been beating humans at complex tasks that seem tailored to the strengths of the human mind, including poker, the game of Go, and visual recognition.

Role of AI in the Industrial Workforce

There are high chances you must have read or heard somewhere “AI IS COMING FOR YOUR JOBS!”

A lot of people think their jobs will be affected by AI but this isn't true. AI will take up mostly routine tasks and not jobs which need cognitive thinking. This simply means that humans will be left for higher-level jobs which will, in turn, boost their morale.

Consciousness is almost impossible to achieve in AI with the technology we currently have. It's like we're still stone-age men when the idea of building consciousness in AI is taken into consideration

This will be beneficial to us as humans get bored by daily routine tasks which hamper their productivity and job satisfaction. Handing down these jobs to AI will actually work in our favour. For many high-stakes decisions that still need logical reasoning, like doctors diagnosing patients and judges setting bail, experts often favour experience and intuition over data and statistics. This reluctance to adopt formal statistical methods makes sense. Thus, these kinds of jobs won't be completely automated, there will always be scope for humans in fields like these which need critical thinking. AI will also take over jobs which are risky and life-threatening. For example, in bomb defusing, mining etc. robots can save thousands of lives. Businesses will need to change their organizational structure to adapt to AI. Humans and AI together will make up the workforce for organizations and will work together for the benefit and profit of industries.

Is AI Really a Threat?

There was a recent debate on the topic “Is AI an existential threat or a great leap forward?” Needless to say, a lot of lousy science fiction movies have tricked us into thinking AI is a threat to human race. We are all familiar with such movies and have come across such poorly thought out scientific cinema which is solely based on earning good revenue. The truth is AGI is very beneficial to humans if built properly, undertaking AI safety measures which are yet being researched by scientists worldwide. It may also be that the media have made the AI safety debate seem more controversial than it really is. After all, fear sells, and articles using out-of-context quotes to proclaim imminent doom can generate more clicks than nuanced and balanced ones (Naudé and Dimitri, 2020).

Many AI researchers roll their eyes when they see this headline: “Stephen Hawking warns that the rise of robots may be disastrous for mankind” (Hawking, 2014). And many have lost count of how many similar articles they’ve seen. Typically, these articles are accompanied by an evil-looking robot carrying a weapon, and they suggest we should worry about robots rising up and killing us because they’ve become conscious or evil. On a lighter note, such articles are actually rather impressive, because they summarize the scenario that AI researchers don’t worry about, the scenario that combines as many as three separate misconceptions: concern about consciousness, evil and robots. Consciousness is almost impossible to achieve in AI with the technology we currently have. It’s like we’re still stone-age men when the idea of building consciousness in AI is taken into consideration.

If the goals of humans and AI machines are aligned, we have nothing to fear. The concern about advanced AI isn’t

malevolence but competence. A super-intelligent AI will be extremely good at accomplishing its goals, and if those goals aren't aligned with ours, we have a problem. You're probably not an evil ant-hater who steps on ants out of malice, but if you're in charge of a hydroelectric green energy project and there's an anthill in the region to be flooded, too bad for the ants. A key goal of AI safety research is to never place humanity in the position of those ants. The main purpose or goal should be communicated to them in order to synchronize the efforts of humans and AI together for the betterment of humanity. There is also no reason for us to be concerned about the intelligence of AI overpowering us since there are always people smarter than us in this world but rather than fearing them, we communicate our ideas and thoughts with them for our own intellect. Similarly, we should learn to communicate ideas with AI robots and encourage their contribution like any other human's for research and development wherever possible. It's about walking hand in hand rather than competing with one another.

The ultimate goal is to use AI to help the human mind, not replace it. The human brain is the most elegant computer in existence. We process millions of sensory inputs automatically and constantly, allowing us to learn and respond to our environment. Imagine the wonders we could do if we complement all of our amazing ideas with not just more data, but also more data processing capability (Venkatachalam 2017). We could rethink every single problem that exists today and work towards finding an optimum solution. Even with today's primitive forms of AI, there is enough technology out there to start doing exactly this. The magnitude of social impact possible when we couple AI with human skill and ingenuity is going to be unbelievable.

Impact of AI on Our Personal Lives

Sophia, a social humanoid robot developed by Hong Kong-based company Hanson Robotics was enough to fascinate millennials worldwide with her human-like gestures, facial expressions and speech during interactions. Ben Goertzel, the former chief scientist for the company that made Sophia, acknowledged that it is not ideal that some think of Sophia as having human-equivalent intelligence, Sophia's presentation conveys something unique to audiences: "If I show them a beautiful smiling robot face, then they get the feeling that 'AGI' (artificial general intelligence) may indeed be nearby and viable."

AI is going to be a boon to us in our personal lives too. Personal Assistant AIs will get to know us and our preferences better as they learn more and more about our daily routines. I can imagine the day I need not worry about preparing dinner. My AI will know what I like, what I have at my home and when I get back from work all my groceries will be waiting at my doorstep, ready for me to prepare that delicious meal I had been craving all day. If you prefer not to cook, it might even cook your desired meal for you and you don't even have to worry about your food being a little bit salty or your *Gajar ka halwa* (carrot pudding) being too sweet for your taste since your AI personal assistant will know exactly how many milligrams of salt you prefer or how sweet you like your *Gajar ka halwa*. AI is going to make a huge difference in our lives at a personal level. It's going to take a huge burden off your shoulders of the minimal tasks you have to do every day for survival, like doing your laundry or dishes or even cleaning your room. You can ask them to do daily chores for you and they won't even complain since they're not going to

get tired of it. You can peacefully go to bed not having to worry about a pile of clothes staring at you the next morning!

I believe that the focus of AI should not be just on cool home gadgets or on process optimization and automation. Instead, AI can be used to fundamentally rethink how we solve the world's problems. AI has the potential to greatly improve things like healthcare, education, poverty, security and various environmental issues. AI machines have done some very beneficial things already that humans would take a long time to do. If we leverage that to augment what humans do well, AI could positively impact society, business and culture along with the internet itself.

AI: Education

Researchers are also constantly looking at how AI can reshape and inform the modern classroom, for teachers and students alike. Personalized tutoring programs help students in everyday learning and analyze how students process information. Whenever students have doubt it's easier to provide additional, customized support with the help of AI. This software is especially helpful for students with learning disabilities, ensuring they receive an individualized approach that matches their needs. Other AI applications include services that automate common teacher tasks, such as marking tests or recording grades for future evaluation. It helps on a large scale in conducting online examinations for institutions worldwide.

AI: Businesses

AI has the potential to increase industrial growth. An amazing example of this is Walmart. While so many other legacy retailers are struggling, Walmart has posted growth figures for the last 11 consecutive quarters. Notably, this has been driven by a 63% year-on-year increase in online sales all with the help of Artificial Intelligence and predictive analytics. Walmart takes data instantaneously from its point-of-sale systems and incorporates this within its forecasts to assess which products are likely to sell

out and which have underperformed. Walmart has received much acclaim for its willingness to adapt to the digital age and its ability to link the online and offline worlds to compete with Amazon.

AI: Transportation

AI has stepped into many fields that indirectly affect our personal lives. One of such fields is transportation. Driverless trains and metro subway systems are being used at various levels throughout the world. While fully autonomous cars are still in the distance, Tesla recently announced that its Model S car is now semi-autonomous, and they released this feature to tens of thousands of already owned cars via a software update. With rising use of autonomous cars and autonomous vehicles in general which run on batteries rather than fuel has turned out to be really beneficial for the environment.

AI: Security

AI applications ranging from personal home alarms to international surveillance are being implemented everywhere around us. AI plays a massive role in keeping individuals and countries safe. Services like intelligent video surveillance analyze footage to identify and report unusual behaviour. AI also helps enforce cybersecurity by identifying abnormalities in online patterns. In digital world, AI helps keep data secure and helps us to communicate and take on our day to day online activities without the fear of compromising our personal information.

AI: Environment

Artificial Intelligence also finds application in a wide array of environmental sectors, including resource conservation, wildlife protection, energy management, clean energy, waste management, pollution control etc. Controlling industrial emissions and waste management is a challenge that can be dealt with the advanced learning machines and smart networks that could detect leaks, potential hazards and

diversions from industry standards and governmental rules. For example, IoT (Internet of Things) technology which interconnects various computing devices embedded in everyday objects, enabling them to send and receive data, was incorporated into several industrial ventures, from refrigerators to thermostats and even retail shops.

As scientists still struggle to predict climate changes and other potential environmental threats due to lack of algorithms for converting the collected useful data into required solutions, Microsoft's AI for Earth, a 50 million dollar initiative, was announced in 2017 with the sole purpose to find solutions to various challenges related to climatic change, agriculture, water and biodiversity.

Conclusion

To sum it all up, I would like to quote Rodney Brooks "Artificial intelligence is a tool, not a threat." AI is already here! True, the technology is still in its inception phase, but intelligent systems are fast learners and we can expect to see significant transformations in near future. Some sectors are at the start of their AI journey, others are veteran travellers. Both have a long way to go. We're going to unlock new possibilities at every level with the help of AI and might even find answers we've been searching for along the journey. AI is a boon to humanity given that all safety measures are undertaken and the ultimate goal is the betterment of mankind and life in general. The change in AI technology is going to be revolutionary. Being human in the age of AI is going to require us to retain the qualities that make us human, such as the ability to love, have compassion and to be creative as well as open our minds to various possibilities that AI brings. The age of AI is inevitable, are you prepared for the future?

References

Golden, Hallie. 2020. "'Just Walk out': Amazon Debuts Its First Supermarket with No Checkout Lines." *The Guardian*.

- Retrieved October 4, 2020 (<https://www.theguardian.com/us-news/2020/feb/25/amazon-go-grocery-super-market-seattle-technology>).
- Hawking, Stephen. 2014. "The rise of robots may be disastrous for mankind." <https://www.worldbulletin.net/>. Retrieved October 4, 2020 (<https://www.worldbulletin.net/sciencetechnology/hawking-the-rise-of-robots-may-be-disastrous-for-mankind-h135701.html>).
- Naudé, Wim, and Nicola Dimitri. 2020. "The Race for an Artificial General Intelligence: Implications for Public Policy." *AI & SOCIETY* 35(2):367–79. doi: 10.1007/s00146-019-00887-x.
- Venkatachalam, Sandhya. 2017. "3 Ways Artificial Intelligence Will Change the World for the Better." *World Economic Forum*. Retrieved October 4, 2020 (<https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2017/05/artificial-intelligence-will-change-the-world-heres-how/>).

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